

DURABILITY OF FIBRE REINFORCED COMPOSITE MATERIALS AFTER TWENTY YEARS OF EXPOSURE TO WEATHERING

A. Yoosefinejad and P. J. Hogg

*Queen Mary and Westfield College,
Department of Materials,
Mile End Road, London E1 4NS, UK*

SUMMARY: Two GRP panels (a bus shelter and a building panel) of 12 and 20 years old respectively were obtained and their service histories were established. Test specimens were prepared to mechanically characterise the weathered panels. Fresh GRP panels were obtained from the manufacturers and the test data from them were used to establish the effect of 20 years of weathering on the GRP panels. No significant deterioration in the moduli of the weathered panels was observed. The tensile and flexural strengths of the bus shelter has shown a 40% decrease in comparison with the fresh panels.

KEYWORDS: durability, GRP, weathering, mechanical properties of GRP

INTRODUCTION

Although the use of fibre reinforced composite (FRC) materials is becoming wide spread in construction, their use dates back to the late sixties and early seventies as fascia panels mostly for aesthetic purposes. One such panel has come to our possession at QMW. The panel was installed in a council housing estate (Elgin Towers, London) which was subsequently demolished in 1993 and this particular panel (Panel A) was saved from destruction and finally found its way to QMW. The panel was estimated to be 20 years old and its primary purpose was as a cladding panel. It had no structural role but was subjected to environmental attack. The panel was exposed to open air on one side and the inner face was insulated with polyurethane foam.

The panel, Fig. 1, was divided into two and one half was used to determine its mechanical properties and the fibre volume fraction.

At the same time as the panel arriving at QMW, London Transport (LT) was in the process of upgrading London bus shelters with a new design and one of the bus shelters was situated outside the Engineering building of QMW. After it was dismantled the roof of the shelter was donated to us. The shelter consisted of a metal frame and chopped strand mat composite panel (Panel B), Fig. 2. LT were able to provide us with the date of manufacture and the name of the manufacturers. The shelter was in service from 1983-1995. The manufacturer gave us the details of the material and two further plates were sent to us (Panel C and D) which represented the same lay up as the old bus shelter. All panels were mechanically characterised.

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of panel A

THE AIMS

- to establish mechanical properties of the panels
- to determine their constituents
- to manufacture similar panels using more or less the same type of materials used in the construction of the old panels
- to provide a better understanding of the degree of degradation due to exposure to twenty and twelve years of weathering by comparing the properties of the old and new panels

MECHANICAL CHARACTERISATION

The specimens were prepared according to ASTM standards. The samples were cut from the panels and no additional cleaning was under-taken, unless strain gauges were necessary to carry out testing. The panels showed typical matrix cracking on the exposed surfaces, particularly so on the bus shelter. Closer inspection of the bus shelter gel coat showed voids filled with dust and airborne particles such as vehicle emission which were consolidated in the voids, perhaps by rain water. In some areas of the panel signs of rust spots were observed which were perhaps caused by metallic particles thrown about in the air by vehicles. There was no evidence that damage caused by the environment had penetrated the gel coat to the fibre and resin layer.

Mechanical test data revealed that panel A had superior mechanical properties in comparison to panel B, as shown in Tables 1 and 2. The reason for this became apparent by further burn-off test on the two panels; the fibre content of the panel A was twice the amount obtained from panel B. The average thickness of the both panels is the same, but the bus shelter was gel coated on the both sides and average thickness of the gel coat was measured to be 0.6 mm. The data generated for panels C and D provided a base line to determine the degradation of the panel B. The stiffness values were very close compared with the weathered materials but there was a marked difference in the strength values. Panels C and D yielded strength values of almost twice the values obtained from panel B.

Table 1: Tensile test data for panels A and B

Tensile test ASTM D3039	Fibre volume fraction %	Young's Modulus (GPa)	Tensile strength (MPa)
Panel A	25 - 30	9.0±1	76.2±10.3
Panel B	14 - 15	4.5±0.6	47.3±9.3

Table 2: Flexure test data for panels A and B

Flexure test ASTM D790M	Fibre volume fraction %	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)
Panel A	25 - 30	11.9±0.6	135.3±2.8
Panel B	14 - 15	5.50±0.3	60.1±4.4

Table 3: Tensile data for panels C and D

Tensile test ASTM D3039	Plate thickness (mm)	Young's Modulus (GPa) Resin : glass ratio = 2.4	Tensile strength (MPa)
Panel C	1.74	4.5±0.4	75.2±4.1
Panel D	3.0	4.70±0.3	84.9±10.7

The tensile and flexure data reported in Ref. 1 and 2 do correspond with the data generated here at a given volume fraction.

Table 4: Flexure test data for panels C and D

Flexure test ASTM D790M	Plate thickness (mm)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)
Panel C	1.74	6.3±0.4	119.6±5.6
Panel D	3.0	7.1±0.7	94.4±4.1

The impact properties of panels A and B are shown in Table 5. The variation in the impact data between panels A and B follow the same trend as tensile and flexure data. All the impact specimens were fractured and the total energy absorption and maximum force were noted, Fig. 3. The total energy absorption of both plates was slightly below that expected for this general class of materials as shown in Fig. 4, Ref. 2. The impact data illustrated in Fig. 4 is a master curve of energy absorption versus volume fraction drawn through data for SMCs and wet lay-up GRPs in general. The below average response of panel B could also be linked to the surface degradation of the gel coat on the panel.

Table 5: Impact properties of panels A and B

	Thickness (mm)	Fibre volume fraction %	Force (N)	Energy absorption (Joules)
Panel A	2.9	28-30	4500	13.7
Panel B	2.9	14 - 15	1500	30

LONG TERM DATA

There is limited long term weathering data on chopped strand mat composite materials and one of such study was published by Norris et al. [3]. They reported an average increase of 15% in tensile modulus during a two year study. The increase was due to the effect of radiation which in turn increased the post curing. The flexural modulus was reported to decrease by 15 - 20% for the same duration, since flexural modulus depends on the surface properties and since weathering degrades surfaces (as was observed on panels A and B) causing a reduction in flexural modulus.

CONCLUSION

The panels A and B were not exposed to any structural load for any significant period of time and the only major attack had been due to the natural environment of the panels. The bus shelter perhaps was more exposed to such conditions than the building panel since the bus shelter was situated on a busy main road. The gel coat contained cracks and as a result of which rain water and other effluents could have reached the fibres and the matrix. Mechanical test data had shown no significant deterioration in the stiffness of the panel B, but a significant decrease in the strengths of the panel in comparison with the fresh samples was observed. This deterioration in strength has been primarily due to weathering. There were no direct comparisons made with panel A since none of the panels tested were of the same volume fraction. Thus only mechanical test data is reported and relative comparison can be made with panels B, C and D.

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Fig. 2: Photograph of the bus shelter prior to its removal

Fig. 3: Building panel specimen after impact

Fig. 4: Energy absorption as function of plate thickness and fibre volume fraction